

All that glitters is not a deduction

Non-deductive methods in computational modelling
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Michal Hladky
University of Geneva
Geneva, Switzerland

Sections

8. Formal Philosophy of Science

1. General Philosophy of Science
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Short abstract

Computational modelling and simulations are often compared with experiments. It has been argued that these methods should be distinguished from experiments, that they are theoretical or that they require new epistemology. Many of these positions are based on the intuition that as these methods rely on computation which can be reconstructed as series of deductive steps, the results they produce are conclusions of deductive arguments. Through a model-theoretical reconstruction of *in silico* experiments, I will demonstrate that the deductivist framework is not entirely adequate to capture their epistemology. Consequently, deduction is not an adequate criterion demarcating simulations from experiments.

Extended abstract

Computational modelling and simulation methods are often compared with experiments. It has been argued that these methods should be distinguished from experiments based on ontological or epistemic differences. The interest of finding acceptable demarcating criteria goes beyond the attempts to provide definitions, characterisations or dividing lines for the methodological landscape of contemporary scientific techniques. Pertinent demarcating criteria should be informative for assessing the relative epistemic powers of various techniques.

Many authors share the intuition that as computer models and simulations rely on computation and computational steps can be reconstructed as deductive steps, deduction should play the central role in the epistemic reconstructions of these methods. Interestingly, computation and deduction feature in the arguments for seemingly incompatible positions about computer models and simulations. Beisbart (2012; 2018) and Beisbart and Norton (2012), the proponents of the argument view of computer simulations, provide deductive reconstructions of deterministic and non-deterministic (stochastic/Monte Carlo) simulations, using these as a support for their claim that these methods are theoretical and not experimental. Humphreys (1994) claims that these methods can be understood as *sui generis* numerical experimentation, but they require a new epistemology. One of the main reasons for this is that although computation

follows a series of deductive steps, individually verifiable by human agents, large simulations lead to epistemic opacity due to an overwhelming number of steps and due to the weak emergence (Humphreys 2008; 2009; Bedau [1997 2008; 2010]). Boge (2018), contrary to Beisbart (2012; 2018), claims that computer simulations are surrogate experiments (rather than surrogates of experiments). While accepting Beisbart's view that the computer simulations "respect the logic of (deductively valid) arguments, they neither agree with their pragmatics nor their epistemology." As the saying goes, in theory there is no difference between theory and practice, while in practice there is. The differences in the positions can be attributed to different conceptions of the relevant epistemic agent performing the inferences leading to knowledge production. While Beisbart takes the relevant agent to be the computer system and the scientist, based on the extended cognition framework, Humphreys and Boge take the perspective of a scientist.

Focusing the debate concerning the epistemology of computational modelling on their deductive features is, *prima facie*, a natural and very intuitive idea, due to the close connection between computation and corresponding deduction. Distinguishing between computer simulations and experiments based on the computational and deductive features also seems to be quite practical. But as another saying goes, that works very well in practice, but how does it work in theory?

In silico experiments are peculiar scientific methods based on computational modelling and simulations. Through a model theoretic reconstruction of a case study from the Blue Brain Project (Markram et al. 2015), I demonstrate the limits of the deductivist picture of computer simulations. I will set aside the obvious obstacles for the deductivist view related to the discretisation and idealisation of the background theories and approximations of the roundoff errors, which are noted by its proponents Beisbart (2012), although not fully recognised as such (Fillion 2022). Instead, I show that even with a strong assumption of a correct computational model (algorithm that will play a role of a theory), the results of *in silico* experiments are *i*) not derived by a deductive inference *ii*) and not directly deducible from the theory (implemented algorithm). Although every inference can ultimately be transformed into a valid, deductive argument by complementing it with suitable assumptions, these come sometimes at an untenable costs.

In the first part, I expose the BBP dynamical computational model of the neocortical tissue, the method deployed to study its behaviour and one of the resulting causal claims relating the concentration of calcium and the transition between the synchronous and asynchronous behaviour of the circuit crucial for cognitive functions of the brain. Subsequently, I translate the case study into model theoretic framework suitable to elucidate relations between the source and target systems and their theoretical descriptions.

I show that an attempt to obtain the resulting causal claim of *in silico* experiments by a deductive inference from the implemented algorithm faces the following difficulties (of increasing magnitude).

The first, minor problem is due to the predicate mismatch between the languages of the source and the target and requires an adoption of a relaxed set of interpretation functions for the terms of the source theory.

The second problem is related to predicates describing the emerging observed behaviours and is analogous to the problem of non-homogeneous reduction (Nagel [1970] 2008) and expressibility of new predicates in terms of old ones.

The third problem is due to the fact that algorithms used in the BBP are non-deterministic. It is clear that even non-deterministic algorithms require semantic saturation (Barberousse, Franceschelli, and Imbert 2009) in order to run on classical computers used in BBP. This is provided by the pseudo-random number generators. Contrary to Beisbart and Norton (2012), claiming that such simulations can be captured by meta-theoretic deduction of the Monte-Carlo form, no statistical arguments were deployed in the case of BBP. The causal claims were derived from observation of particular instances of the algorithm. And although these instances were computationally generated from the background

algorithm, supplemented by a particular random sequences, and as such obtained deductively, in order to generate the resulting causal claim, the particularity of the sequences has to be abstracted away.

The fourth, main problem is due to the nature of emergent properties observed in particular set of observed models. This emergence is distinct from the weak emergence understood as computational incompressibility (Humphreys 1994; 2008) and is generated by the sampling of particular instances from the set of all theoretical models. In short, due to the incompleteness of the theory relative to the sample set. Contrary to the deductivist view, the emergent properties and related new knowledge about the causal relations are not and should not be considered as examples of theory use, but of theory construction.

Although every inference can be transformed into a formally valid deduction, the transformation comes at an epistemic price. The above-mentioned issues show the inadequacy of the deductivist picture applied to *in silico* experiments deployed in BBP and points to a different kind of inference akin to creative abduction (Schurz 2008, see also Magnani 2001) and a reliabilist epistemic justification, expanding Durán and Formanek (2018) analysis focusing on epistemic opacity.

References

- Barberousse, Anouk, Sara Franceschelli, and Cyrille Imbert. 2009. 'Computer Simulations as Experiments'. *Synthese* 169 (3): 557–74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-008-9430-7>.
- Bedau, Mark A. (1997) 2008. 'Weak Emergence'. *Noûs* 31 (June): 375–99. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0029-4624.31.s11.17>.
- . 2010. 'Weak Emergence and Context-Sensitive Reduction'. In *Emergence in Science and Philosophy*, edited by Antonella Corradini and Timothy O'Connor, 0 ed. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203849408>.
- Beisbart, Claus. 2012. 'How Can Computer Simulations Produce New Knowledge?' *Euro Jnl Phil Sci* 2 (3): 395–434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13194-012-0049-7>.
- . 2018. 'Are Computer Simulations Experiments? And If Not, How Are They Related to Each Other?' *European Journal for Philosophy of Science* 8 (2): 171–204. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13194-017-0181-5>.
- Beisbart, Claus, and John D. Norton. 2012. 'Why Monte Carlo Simulations Are Inferences and Not Experiments'. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science* 26 (4): 403–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02698595.2012.748497>.
- Boge, Florian J. 2018. 'Why Computer Simulations Are Not Inferences, and in What Sense They Are Experiments'. *European Journal for Philosophy of Science* 9 (1): 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13194-018-0239-z>.
- Durán, Juan M., and Nico Formanek. 2018. 'Grounds for Trust: Essential Epistemic Opacity and Computational Reliabilism'. *Minds and Machines* 28 (4): 645–66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-018-9481-6>.
- Fillion, Nicolas. 2022. 'The Logic and Semantics of Approximation in Models and Their Solutions'. Presented at the Fourth conference of East European Network for Philosophy of Science - EENPS 2022 (17-19/08/2022), University of Tartu, Estonia, August 17.
- Humphreys, Paul. 1994. 'Numerical Experimentation'. In *Patrick Suppes, Scientific Philosopher*, edited by Patrick Suppes and Paul Humphreys, 103–21. Synthese Library, v. 235. Dordrecht ; Boston: Kluwer Academic.
- . 2008. 'Computational and Conceptual Emergence'. *Philosophy of Science* 75 (5): 584–94. <https://doi.org/10.1086/596776>.
- . 2009. 'The Philosophical Novelty of Computer Simulation Methods'. *Synthese* 169 (3): 615–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-008-9435-2>.
- Magnani, Lorenzo. 2001. *Abduction, Reason, and Science: Processes of Discovery and Explanation*. New York: Springer.
- Markram, Henry, Eilif Muller, Srikanth Ramaswamy, Michael W. Reimann, Marwan Abdellah, Carlos Aguado Sanchez, Anastasia Ailamaki, et al. 2015. 'Reconstruction and Simulation of Neocortical Microcircuitry'. *Cell* 163 (2): 456–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2015.09.029>.
- Nagel, Ernest. (1970) 2008. 'Issues in the Logic of Reductive Explanations'. In *Emergence: Contemporary Readings in Philosophy and Science*, edited by Mark A. Bedau and Paul Humphreys, 359–73. The MIT Press. <http://mitpress.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.7551/mitpress/9780262026215.001.0001/upso-9780262026215-chapter-19>.
- Schurz, G. 2008. 'Patterns of Abduction'. *Synthese* 164 (2): 201–34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-007-9223-4>.